

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 3, March- 2023 | Peer-Reviewed Journal
ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10105049

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SUPPORT TEACHER FOR THE COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT OF AUTISTIC STUDENTS: A CASE STUDY IN A STATE SCHOOL IN GOIATUBA, GOIÁS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to analyze whether students with Autism Spectrum Disorder have the ability to develop their cognitive skills in the school context and the importance of the Support Teacher in this process as a key element for learning to take place. Future work should be more comprehensive and address all students diagnosed with autism in state, municipal and private schools.